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Towards a Metadata Scheme for Energy Research Software

Abstract for the 2. NFDI4Energy Conference 2025

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Abstract:

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Ferez et al. [1] define Energy Research Software (ERS) as software used in the scientific discovery process for understanding, analyzing, improving, and designing energy systems. ERS can be found at different levels of complexity, from basic scripts or libraries, e.g., in Python, to complete software solutions. In terms of content, ERS may involve visualization, analysis, and generation of (artificial) data associated with energy systems, components, or grids (from laboratories or the real world). Moreover, ERS can also represent specific energy components, systems, and their transition paths in terms of energy usage, distribution, conversion, and generation for evaluations in simulations and optimizations. [1] By providing these various functionalities, ERS heavily supports research in the energy domain and presents the foundation for different research results in energy research.

The development of ERS is facing multiple challenges, e.g., through the increasing complexity of energy systems and of research itself [1]. Metadata have been shown to be one of the success factors for the so-called FAIRification of research software, especially to improve findability and reusability of research software [2]–[4]. To reach a high level of findability, metadata should follow domain-relevant community standards [5]. Therefore, the development of such domain-relevant metadata standards presents a key prerequisite to enable FAIR ERS [1].

We gave a detailed overview on related metadata schemes in [1]. While some general metadata schemes for research software focus on some main properties, like *CodeMeta*¹, others try to include detailed domain knowledge based on domain ontologies like *biotoolsXSD* [6] (for Life Science) or the *Software Description Ontology* [7]

¹<https://codemeta.github.io/>, accessed 20.10.2023

(for Geoscience). In the energy domain, a formalized metadata scheme for ERS is still missing. However, the open energy platform², the openmod wiki³, and the work of Schwarz and Lehnhoff [8] present good starting points for developing a formalized metadata scheme for ERS.

None of these approaches used a formalized and interoperable metadata scheme to open the approach for further reuse for FAIR ERS. Also, none of the approaches are based on a requirement analysis, which is important to identify meaningful metadata elements [9]. A requirement analysis should be the first step in developing a metadata scheme to identify the information that should be included in the metadata [9]⁴. Based on the requirements, it can be analyzed if an existing scheme can be extended or which elements from existing schemes can be reused.

Accelerated by these motivations, we performed a requirement analysis for a metadata scheme for ERS by conducting interviews with over 30 energy researchers [11]. Based on this requirement analysis and by carefully analysing related schemes, we developed a metadata scheme for ERS which we would like to present and discuss with the audience.

Therefore, we shortly describe our method in the following. Finally, we conclude the abstract.

2 Method

The metadata scheme should be developed as an application profile. An application profile combines existing metadata elements from different ontologies and schemes into a new metadata scheme for specific use cases [10] here to describe ERS. We based our method on existing methods like the approach of Curado Malta and Baptista [12].

In the first step, requirements for the metadata scheme were collected and a first domain model was developed [11].

As next step, an environmental scan was performed. Within this scan, existing metadata schemes were analyzed and partly mapped to the domain model. CodeMeta¹, the metadata scheme of the Open Energy Platform² and DataDesc [13] were part of this analysis. Based on the analysis, additional elements were added to the domain model. Also, elements were changed to better align with existing schemes.

From the domain model a first list of metadata elements and descriptions were derived. This list also contain the information if an element is mandatory or not. For this first list of metadata elements, feedback from three experts that were not included in the requirements analysis were gathered to further improve the metadata scheme. One expert had a special focus on metadata in the energy domain, one expert focused on ERS and the third expert focused on metadata for ERS. In a next step, the metadata elements will be aligned as good as possible with existing formalized metadata schemes. When an alignment is not possible, mappings between the metadata schemes (crosswalks) will be provided.

²<https://openenergy-platform.org/factsheets/models/>, accessed 26.03.2024

³https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/wiki/Open_Models, accessed 20.10.2023

⁴Instead of developing a completely new metadata scheme, another option is to develop an application profile. An application profile recombines and refines metadata elements from other existing metadata schemes [10] to address a specific application. Nevertheless, the requirements will be the same for both approaches. Therefore, we will use the term metadata scheme for the rest of this abstract.

Afterwards, it will be analyzed which ontologies can be used as value vocabularies for certain terms.

By using the AIMS platform [10] existing and news terms should be combined to a formalized metadata scheme.

3 Conclusion

Metadata is central to make ERS more FAIR. A domain-specific metadata scheme is a key prerequisite to enable the use of metadata for ERS. Based on a requirement analysis, we developed a metadata scheme for ERS. We want to present and discuss our preliminary metadata scheme for ERS on the NFDI4Energy conference. The metadata scheme is highly relevant in the context of research software management in the energy domain and we would like to discuss it with the NFDI4Energy community.

Author contributions

Stephan Ferez contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing - original draft. Oliver Werth contributed in methodology and writing - review & editing. Astrid Nieße contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing - review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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